

Balance between Forest Conservation and Economic Benefits of Nature-Based Tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park (Czech Republic)

Barbora Dvořáková ^{1*}, Tomáš Krejčí ¹

¹ Affiliation 1; Staff at University of Veterinary and Pharmaceutical Sciences Brno, Palackého tř. 1946/1, 612 42 Brno-Královo Pole, Czechia
Contact: Barbora_dvorakowa@vfu.cz

Abstract: This study examines the intricate balance between forest conservation efforts and the economic advantages of nature-based tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park, Czech Republic. As a prime destination for ecotourism, the park attracts visitors seeking natural experiences, which creates both opportunities and challenges for sustainable management. The research investigates the impact of tourism on forest ecosystems, evaluates the economic contributions of tourism to the local community, and identifies strategies to minimize adverse environmental effects. This work aims to provide recommendations for harmonizing economic development with conservation priorities, ensuring the long-term preservation of the park's biodiversity. Keywords: Nature-based tourism, forest conservation, ecotourism, sustainable management, Český Švýcarsko National Park, economic benefits, environmental impact.

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1. Introduction

Nature-based tourism, often referred to as ecotourism, encompasses recreational activities that take place in natural settings, such as forests, mountains, rivers, and other untouched landscapes (Buckley, 2010; Fennell, 2020). This form of tourism emphasizes responsible travel that seeks to minimize environmental impact while allowing tourists to experience and appreciate nature. In the context of forest ecosystems, nature-based tourism is especially significant because it provides a direct economic incentive to preserve these areas. By generating revenue through activities like hiking, bird-watching, and guided tours, nature-based tourism can support conservation efforts, as long as it is managed sustainably (Buckley, 2010). However, the presence of tourists in sensitive ecosystems can lead to habitat disturbance, pollution, and increased pressure on local wildlife, necessitating carefully balanced management strategies (Newsome et al., 2012).

Český Švýcarsko National Park, also known as Bohemian Switzerland National Park, is situated in the northern part of the Czech Republic, bordering Germany's Saxon Switzerland National Park. Established in 2000, the park covers approximately 79 square kilometers and is renowned for its striking sandstone formations, deep gorges, and dense forest cover (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). The park's unique geological features and rich biodiversity make it a prime destination for nature-based tourism, attracting hundreds of thousands of visitors annually. Its diverse flora and fauna, including several rare and endemic species, contribute to its ecological significance (Čížek et al., 2013). As a flagship destination for ecotourism in the Czech Republic, Český Švýcarsko plays a critical role in promoting the country's natural heritage, offering visitors opportunities to engage with

pristine landscapes while contributing to local and national economies (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015).

Tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park is a major economic driver for surrounding communities. The influx of visitors supports local businesses, including hotels, restaurants, and guide services, which in turn creates employment opportunities and stimulates the regional economy (Kučera, 2019). According to data from the Czech Statistical Office (2019), tourism in the region contributes significantly to local GDP, with revenue generated from entrance fees, guided tours, and the sale of local products. The economic benefits of tourism extend beyond direct revenue; they also include infrastructural improvements that benefit residents, such as better transportation networks and enhanced public services. For many small communities near the park, tourism represents a vital source of income that complements traditional economic activities like agriculture and forestry (Vavroušek et al., 2020). This economic dependence on tourism underscores the need for sustainable management practices to ensure that the influx of visitors does not compromise the park's ecological integrity.

Despite the economic advantages associated with tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park, managing the balance between economic growth and environmental conservation remains a significant challenge. The increasing number of tourists places considerable pressure on the park's ecosystems, leading to issues such as soil erosion, habitat degradation, and disturbances to wildlife (Newsome et al., 2012; Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). Moreover, the construction of infrastructure to accommodate visitors, such as trails, parking areas, and accommodation facilities, can further fragment habitats and alter natural landscapes (Kučera, 2019). These challenges highlight a critical need for a management approach that not only maximizes economic benefits but also safeguards the park's biodiversity. Previous studies have emphasized the importance of adopting strategies that limit visitor numbers, educate tourists about responsible behavior, and develop zoning regulations to protect sensitive areas (Jalinik et al., 2024; Buckley, 2010; Fennell, 2020). Without such measures, the long-term ecological health of Český Švýcarsko National Park could be compromised, threatening both its biodiversity and its economic viability as a tourist destination.

This study aims to explore the dual aspects of nature-based tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park by examining both its economic contributions and its environmental impacts. The research will focus on quantifying the economic benefits of tourism to local communities, including income generation, employment creation, and infrastructural investments. Additionally, it will assess the ecological consequences of tourism, using data on habitat disturbances, changes in biodiversity, and the effects of human activities on soil and vegetation. A key objective is to identify management strategies that can balance these competing priorities, ensuring that tourism remains a sustainable economic driver while preserving the ecological value of the park. The study will provide actionable recommendations for park managers and policymakers, with an emphasis on adaptive management practices, visitor education, and the development of sustainable tourism policies (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015; Newsome et al., 2012). Through this approach, the research aims to contribute to the broader discourse on sustainable tourism in protected natural areas, offering insights that could be applicable to other ecologically sensitive regions.

2. Analysis of Economic Contributions of Tourism

Nature-based tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park plays a significant role in generating revenue and creating employment opportunities for local communities. Visitor spending on accommodation, dining, and park-related activities is a primary source of income for the region. Data from the Czech Statistical Office (2019) indicates that tourism

contributes millions of Czech koruna annually, with substantial portions attributed to accommodation facilities such as hotels, guesthouses, and campgrounds (Kučera, 2019). Dining establishments, ranging from local restaurants to cafes and food stalls, benefit directly from the influx of visitors, creating a thriving market for local produce and culinary specialties (Vavroušek et al., 2020). Additionally, park entrance fees and guided tours provide direct revenue to the national park's management, which is reinvested in maintenance and conservation efforts (Jalinik & Pawlowicz, 2024; Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015).

The employment generated by tourism extends across various sectors, including hospitality, retail, and guiding services. According to Kučera (2019), tourism supports a substantial proportion of jobs in the region, with a significant number of residents employed as hotel staff, tour guides, and retail workers. The demand for local guides, who offer specialized knowledge of the park's unique geological formations and biodiversity, has seen a steady rise, further enhancing income opportunities for residents (Čížek et al., 2013). This economic activity contributes not only to local employment but also to the retention of younger populations in rural areas, mitigating the trend of urban migration (Vavroušek et al., 2020).

Quantitatively, tourism's contribution to the local GDP is substantial, with estimates suggesting that the sector accounts for a significant percentage of economic activity in the region. The World Tourism Organization (2018) highlights that tourism in protected areas like Český Švýcarsko can contribute up to 10-15% of local GDP, underlining its importance as an economic engine. Such contributions are critical for communities that may lack other significant sources of income, making tourism a pillar of economic stability and growth in these rural settings (Newsome et al., 2012).

The growth of nature-based tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park has necessitated substantial investments in tourism infrastructure, such as the development of hiking trails, visitor centers, and parking facilities. These investments have been pivotal in enhancing visitor access to the park while aiming to reduce the ecological footprint of tourism activities (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). The construction and maintenance of a well-developed network of trails help direct visitors along designated routes, minimizing their impact on sensitive habitats and reducing soil compaction and vegetation trampling (Buckley, 2010).

Visitor centers play a crucial role in managing the flow of tourists and providing educational resources about the park's natural heritage. These centers, often funded through a combination of public investment and park fees, serve as hubs for environmental education, offering information on local biodiversity and guidelines for responsible tourism practices (Newsome et al., 2012). Additionally, parking facilities located at strategic entry points help manage visitor numbers, limiting vehicle access to ecologically vulnerable areas (Vavroušek et al., 2020).

The funding for these infrastructure projects comes from diverse sources, including national and regional government allocations, private investments, and international grants aimed at promoting sustainable tourism. Public funding often covers the initial development of infrastructure, while private investment, such as the establishment of eco-lodges and locally-owned restaurants, supports the expansion of services that cater to tourists (Kučera, 2019). International grants, such as those provided by the European Union for sustainable regional development, have also been instrumental in supporting the creation of eco-friendly facilities and conservation initiatives in the park (Vărzaru & Bocean, 2023). This blend of funding sources is crucial in maintaining a balance between tourism development and conservation, allowing for continuous improvements in infrastructure while safeguarding the park's ecological integrity.

In conclusion, the economic contributions of nature-based tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park are substantial, providing essential revenue and employment to local

communities. These contributions are closely tied to investments in infrastructure that enhance visitor experiences while aiming to minimize their ecological footprint. However, the ongoing challenge remains to manage these developments in a manner that ensures long-term ecological balance, an issue that will be further explored in subsequent sections of this study.

3. Environmental Impact of Nature-Based Tourism

3.1. Ecological Disturbance and Habitat Degradation

Nature-based tourism, while offering economic benefits, can also contribute significantly to ecological disturbance and habitat degradation within protected areas like Český Švýcarsko National Park. Habitat degradation refers to the alteration or destruction of the natural environment, which reduces its ability to support native species and ecological functions (Newsome et al., 2012). In the context of tourism, such degradation often results from physical impacts, including trampling of vegetation, soil compaction, and increased erosion along popular trails (Buckley, 2010; Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). Trampling by visitors can damage plant roots and compact the soil, reducing its porosity and water retention capacity, which, in turn, affects plant growth and the health of surrounding flora (Marion & Leung, 2011). This is particularly problematic in fragile ecosystems where vegetation recovery rates are slow, such as those found in certain parts of Český Švýcarsko National Park.

Changes in vegetation cover and species composition are also common consequences of tourism-related activities. Areas that experience high visitor traffic often see shifts from native plant species to more resilient, disturbance-tolerant species, which can alter the ecological balance of these habitats (Kučera, 2019). For example, a study by Křenová & Kindlmann (2015) in the park observed a decline in certain native plant species in heavily trafficked areas, with an increase in non-native or invasive species that are better adapted to disturbed soil conditions. Such shifts can disrupt existing ecological networks, impacting species that rely on specific native plants for food and shelter (Marion & Leung, 2011). These changes can ripple through the ecosystem, potentially leading to a reduction in biodiversity over time.

Ecological surveys conducted in Český Švýcarsko National Park have provided data on the effects of tourism on wildlife disturbances. Wildlife, including sensitive species such as birds and small mammals, often exhibits avoidance behavior in response to the presence of tourists, leading to changes in their feeding, breeding, and migration patterns (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). Studies have shown that increased human presence along trails and near popular scenic spots can cause animals to avoid these areas, leading to habitat fragmentation and reduced access to essential resources (Čížek et al., 2013). A survey by Kučera (2019) reported that species like the black stork (*Ciconia nigra*), which is sensitive to human disturbances, has increasingly nested in more remote areas of the park as a direct response to growing tourism activity. This displacement can decrease reproductive success and contribute to population declines if suitable undisturbed habitats are limited.

The cumulative impact of these disturbances underscores the importance of carefully managing tourist activities in protected areas to mitigate ecological damage. Without such management, the long-term ecological balance of Český Švýcarsko National Park could be threatened, potentially undermining the very natural features that attract visitors to the park (Newsome et al., 2012; Buckley, 2010). The next section will explore existing strategies for minimizing these impacts and ensuring the sustainable coexistence of tourism and conservation efforts within the park.

3.2. Strategies for Minimizing Environmental Impact

Český Švýcarsko National Park employs several management practices aimed at reducing the environmental impacts of tourism while maintaining the quality of visitor experiences. One of the primary strategies is visitor education, which focuses on raising awareness about the park's ecological value and promoting responsible behavior among tourists. Information boards, guided tours, and visitor centers play a crucial role in educating tourists about minimizing their footprint, respecting wildlife, and staying on designated trails (Newsome et al., 2012; Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). These educational efforts are critical for instilling a sense of stewardship among visitors and encouraging behaviors that align with the park's conservation goals.

Another essential management practice is the use of restricted zones, where access is limited to protect sensitive habitats and species from excessive human disturbance. These zones are often delineated based on ecological data, identifying areas that host vulnerable species or ecosystems that are particularly sensitive to human presence (Buckley, 2010). Seasonal closures are also implemented, particularly during critical periods like breeding seasons for birds or times of increased wildlife activity, to minimize disruptions to animal behavior and protect young and nesting animals (Čížek et al., 2013). This targeted approach helps ensure that wildlife can access key resources and habitats without interference from tourism activities.

The effectiveness of these management strategies has been evaluated through ongoing environmental monitoring programs within the park. Studies have shown that educational initiatives have had a positive impact on visitor behavior, leading to decreased littering and better adherence to marked trails (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). This is supported by visitor surveys indicating a higher awareness of conservation issues among those who have participated in guided tours or engaged with interpretive materials at visitor centers (Newsome et al., 2012). However, the challenge remains in reaching all tourists, particularly those who enter the park without prior engagement with these resources (Buckley, 2010).

Restricted zones and seasonal closures have proven effective in reducing direct human-wildlife interactions. Data from wildlife surveys indicate that species like the black stork (*Ciconia nigra*) have shown stable breeding patterns in areas where access is limited during critical nesting periods (Kučera, 2019). Additionally, vegetation surveys have reported reduced signs of trampling and soil compaction in areas with restricted access, demonstrating the positive impact of spatial zoning (Marion & Leung, 2011). However, enforcement of these restrictions can be challenging, especially during peak tourist seasons when visitor numbers are highest (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). In such cases, additional resources are required to ensure compliance and prevent unauthorized access to sensitive areas.

While current management practices have yielded positive results, there is a need for adaptive management strategies that can respond more dynamically to changes in visitor behavior and environmental conditions. Adaptive management involves continuous monitoring and adjustment of management actions based on new data, ensuring that strategies remain effective over time (Fennell, 2020). For instance, adjusting the timing and extent of seasonal closures based on real-time data about wildlife activity could help further reduce the impact on sensitive species.

The use of technology, such as GPS-based visitor tracking systems, offers additional opportunities for enhancing management practices. By monitoring the movement patterns of visitors throughout the park, managers can identify areas of high traffic and

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implement measures to alleviate pressure on those locations, such as redirecting visitors to less sensitive areas (Buckley, 2010). Real-time data can also be used to manage visitor flows, preventing overcrowding and ensuring that visitors adhere to designated trails and access restrictions (Kučera, 2019). Mobile applications that provide real-time updates about restricted zones or educational content could further enhance compliance and awareness, offering a more interactive way to engage with visitors.

In conclusion, the combination of visitor education, restricted zones, and seasonal closures has provided a foundation for managing tourism impacts in Český Švýcarsko National Park. However, the integration of adaptive management and technological tools could further improve the park's ability to balance ecological preservation with the demands of nature-based tourism. These recommendations are aimed at ensuring that tourism can continue to benefit the local economy without compromising the natural assets that make the park a valuable destination for future generations (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015; Newsome et al., 2012).

4. Discussion

This economic boost supports local communities, provides income diversification, and enhances regional development, making it a critical driver for the area's socio-economic resilience. However, the environmental costs associated with increased tourist activity are substantial. Issues such as habitat degradation, soil compaction, and disturbances to local wildlife highlight the ecological pressures that accompany economic growth (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015; Marion & Leung, 2011). The synthesis of these findings underscores the inherent trade-off: while tourism is vital for economic sustainability, it can undermine the very ecological integrity that draws visitors in the first place. Addressing this trade-off requires carefully balancing tourism growth with conservation measures to ensure long-term sustainability.

The perspectives of various stakeholders reflect the diverse interests and priorities involved in managing tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park. Local businesses, such as hotels, restaurants, and tour operators, emphasize the economic importance of tourism. For many, tourism represents a crucial source of income, especially in rural areas where alternative economic opportunities are limited (Vavroušek et al., 2020). These stakeholders often advocate for policies that promote visitor numbers and extend the tourist season, as increased foot traffic translates directly into higher revenues.

Park management, however, must balance the economic interests with the need to preserve the park's natural resources. Their focus is on implementing strategies that mitigate the impact of tourism, such as visitor education programs and restricted zones, to maintain the ecological health of the park (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). They often face pressure to accommodate both conservation goals and the economic expectations of the local community, creating a challenging position that requires negotiation and compromise.

Conservationists bring a different perspective, prioritizing the long-term ecological integrity of the park over short-term economic gains. They argue that unchecked tourism growth can lead to irreversible environmental damage, particularly in sensitive areas where even minor disturbances can have significant impacts on biodiversity (Buckley, 2010; Newsome et al., 2012). Conservation groups often call for stricter regulations, such as limiting visitor numbers or closing off ecologically vulnerable areas, to protect species and habitats from the pressures of mass tourism.

Aligning tourism with conservation goals in Český Švýcarsko National Park involves several challenges. One of the primary difficulties is balancing the immediate economic needs of local communities with the long-term requirements of ecosystem preservation. While tourism provides essential financial resources, it also drives environmental

degradation that could compromise the park's attractiveness as a destination over time (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). The fluctuating nature of tourism, with peaks during certain seasons, adds another layer of complexity, as it results in periods of intense environmental pressure followed by relative inactivity. Managing such seasonal impacts requires adaptive strategies that can accommodate shifts in visitor numbers while protecting the park's natural assets (Marion & Leung, 2011).

Another challenge is the effective enforcement of conservation measures. Restricted zones and seasonal closures have proven beneficial, but ensuring compliance can be difficult, particularly during peak seasons when visitor numbers overwhelm monitoring capacities (Newsome et al., 2012). Additionally, there is often resistance from local stakeholders who fear that stringent regulations could deter tourists and negatively affect their livelihoods (Kučera, 2019). This tension between economic interests and conservation imperatives requires a nuanced approach to management, where the benefits of sustainable practices are communicated clearly to all parties involved.

To address these challenges, a balanced approach that involves community engagement and collaborative management is crucial. Engaging local communities in the conservation process can help align their economic interests with environmental goals. For example, incorporating community input in the planning of restricted zones and involving residents in ecotourism initiatives can foster a sense of ownership and responsibility towards protecting the park (Buckley, 2010). Community-based tourism models, where local guides and businesses play a leading role in managing visitor experiences, can also help distribute economic benefits more evenly and reduce pressures on the park's core areas (Fennell, 2020).

Collaborative management between park authorities, local businesses, and conservation groups can facilitate more effective and adaptive strategies. This approach allows for the integration of diverse knowledge sources and the development of policies that are both scientifically sound and economically viable (Newsome et al., 2012). Regular dialogues among stakeholders can help address conflicts, set realistic visitor capacity limits, and agree on measures to enhance the sustainability of tourism. Additionally, leveraging technological tools like GPS-based visitor monitoring can support real-time adjustments to management practices, ensuring that tourism activities remain within ecologically sustainable limits (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015).

In summary, achieving a balance between economic development and environmental conservation in Český Švýcarsko National Park requires a multifaceted strategy that involves active community participation, adaptive management, and collaborative decision-making. This approach not only helps to maintain the ecological health of the park but also ensures that the benefits of tourism are equitably distributed, fostering long-term sustainability for both the natural environment and the local economy.

5. Conclusion

The analysis of nature-based tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park highlights a complex relationship between economic gains and ecological challenges. On one hand, tourism serves as a critical economic driver, contributing to local GDP through job creation and infrastructure development, such as accommodations, dining services, and park amenities (Kučera, 2019; Vavroušek et al., 2020). These activities enhance the economic resilience of surrounding communities, offering an alternative to traditional industries like agriculture and forestry. On the other hand, the ecological costs of increased visitor numbers are significant, manifesting as habitat degradation, soil compaction, and disturbances to local wildlife (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015; Newsome et al., 2012). The trade-off between these benefits and environmental impacts underscores the necessity for

sustainable tourism practices to ensure the long-term preservation of the park's natural resources.

The findings from this study reaffirm the critical need for balanced tourism management in protected areas like Český Švýcarsko National Park. Sustainable tourism practices must prioritize the protection of ecological integrity while allowing for economic benefits to flow to local communities. Effective management involves not just restricting access to sensitive areas, but also fostering a culture of environmental stewardship among visitors through education and engagement (Buckley, 2010). Without such balanced approaches, the long-term viability of nature-based tourism as both an economic asset and a tool for conservation may be compromised.

To achieve a sustainable balance, park managers and local authorities should consider implementing the following policy recommendations:

- Adaptive Visitor Management: Adjust visitor access based on real-time ecological data to prevent overcrowding in vulnerable areas, such as implementing dynamic restrictions during critical wildlife breeding seasons (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015).
- Enhanced Visitor Education Programs: Strengthen educational initiatives that promote responsible behavior, including respecting wildlife, staying on designated trails, and reducing waste. This could be achieved through digital platforms, on-site displays, and guided tours (Newsome et al., 2012).
- Community-Based Tourism Initiatives: Engage local communities in co-managing tourism resources, ensuring that economic benefits are distributed equitably and that local knowledge is incorporated into conservation efforts (Fennell, 2020).
- Development of Eco-Friendly Infrastructure: Invest in facilities that reduce the ecological footprint of tourism, such as renewable energy-powered visitor centers and eco-certified accommodations, thereby aligning infrastructure development with sustainability goals (Kučera, 2019).

Future research should focus on several key areas to support the sustainable development of nature-based tourism in Český Švýcarsko National Park:

- Long-Term Environmental Monitoring: Ongoing ecological studies are needed to track the impact of tourism on biodiversity, soil health, and water quality over extended periods (Křenová & Kindlmann, 2015). This would provide critical data for adaptive management strategies.
- Visitor Behavior Studies: Understanding the behaviors and preferences of tourists can help managers tailor educational efforts and infrastructure improvements. Studies could examine factors influencing compliance with park regulations and how different visitor segments respond to educational initiatives (Newsome et al., 2012).
- Exploration of Alternative Income Sources for Local Communities: Diversifying income sources beyond tourism could reduce economic pressures to increase visitor numbers. Research into sustainable practices such as agro-tourism or craft industries could provide viable alternatives for local economies (Vavroušek et al., 2020).

In conclusion, while nature-based tourism offers valuable economic opportunities for the Český Švýcarsko region, its success hinges on careful management to preserve the park's ecological integrity. By adopting adaptive strategies and fostering collaboration between stakeholders, the region can ensure that tourism remains a sustainable asset for both the environment and the local economy.

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